

AN ANALYSIS OF LARGE DEFLECTION BENDING OF
SHALLOW LAMINATED COMPOSITE SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the application of Dynamic Relaxation (DR) method to the problem of large deflection bending of shallow laminated composite shells. The numerical results are given for orthotropic doubly curved shallow shells as well as two-layer, cross-ply cylindrical and doubly curved shallow shells. The results obtained are compared with available data. The phenomenon that central deflection of cylindrical shells may jump to the opposite direction when load increases to some larger value has been found.

MAIN FORMULAE OF ITERATIONS

We consider the shallow shells over a square plane shown in Fig. 1. A certain properly curved panel paralleled with the shell surface and the z-axis is taken in the direction normal to the oxy surface. The radii of curvatures along x-direction and y-direction are denoted as R_x and R_y respectively. According to finite deflection bending equilibrium equations of shallow shells, the corresponding dynamic equations can be written as

Fig. 1

$$N_{1,x} + N_{6,y} = \rho_u \cdot U_{,tt} + \mu_u \cdot U_{,t}$$

$$N_{6,x} + N_{2,y} = \rho_v \cdot V_{,tt} + \mu_v \cdot V_{,t}$$

$$M_{1,xx} + 2M_{6,xy} + M_{2,yy} + N_1 W_{,xx} + 2N_6 W_{,xy} + N_2 W_{,yy} + (N_{1,x} + N_{6,y}) W_{,x} + (N_{6,x} + N_{2,y}) W_{,y} - (N_1/R_x + N_2/R_y) + q_z = \rho_w \cdot W_{,tt} + \mu_w \cdot W_{,t}$$

where ρ_r and μ_r ($r=u,v,w$) are fictitious densities and damping factors respectively; subscript t denotes time.

performing center finite-difference procedure to the above equations, the iterative form formulae for the velocities \dot{U} , \dot{V} and \dot{W} at each nodal point can be written. From $U_{,t} = \dot{U}$, ect., the iterative formulae of displacements U, V and W can be obtained.

The method of calculating fictitious densities may be found in Refs. [1,2]. The damping factors can be evaluated by the method proposed in reference [3].

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In all examples for computation, following clamped boundary condition is considered:

$$U = V = W = W_{,x} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = 0, a$$

$$U = V = W = W_{,y} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = 0, a$$

The problem of large deflection bending of specially orthotropic doubly equal curved shallow shells under uniformly distributed external pressures has been first considered. In the analyses the following geometrical data are used: $a = 15(\text{in})$; $h = 0.193(\text{in})$; $R_x = R_y = 50(\text{in})$, $200(\text{in})$ and ∞ (i.e. orthotropic plate). The material properties used in the analyses are: $E_L = 36.39 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $E_T = 4.79 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $G_{LT} = 1.96 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $\nu_{LT} = 0.3$.

The obtained results are plotted in Figs. 2-3. From the analyzing of the numerical results obtained, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. From Fig. 2 it can be seen that present results for orthotropic plate ($R_x = \infty$ $R_y = \infty$) agree well with the results in Ref. [4].
2. The influence of the curvatures of shallow shells on the deflections are very pronounced. The central deflections of shallow shells with $R_x = R_y = 200(\text{in})$ are larger than that with $R_x = R_y = 50(\text{in})$ under same load.
3. From Fig. 2 it can be seen that when the load increases to a certain extent the central deflection of the shallow shell with very small curvature (e.g. $R_x = R_y = 200(\text{in})$) becomes larger than that of the plate because the deflection of the shell has offsetted the influence of the curvature and it has become almost flat panel, and the plate has become curved.
4. From Fig. 3 it is demonstrated that for the shell with $R_x = R_y = 50(\text{in})$ the jump of deflection may occur when the load increases to $160(\text{psi})$.

The problem of large deflection bending of laminated composite shallow shells subjected to uniformly distributed external pressures has been considered. In the computations, $a = 508(\text{in})$; $h = 2.54(\text{in})$; and R_x and R_y are chosen as following three cases: (a) $R_x = R_y = 2540(\text{in})$, (b) $R_x = R_y = \infty$ (i.e. laminate), (c) $R_x = \infty$ and $R_y = 2540(\text{in})$ (i.e. cylindrically shallow shell). The material properties used in the analyses are: $E_L = 40 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $E_T = 10^6 (\text{psi})$, $G_{LT} = 0.6 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $\nu_{LT} = 0.25$. The obtained results are plotted in Fig. 4-5. From the analyzing of the numerical results obtained, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. From Fig. 4 it can be seen that under same load the central deflections of the doubly equal curved shallow shell are less than that of the cylindrically shallow shell, and when load is lower the central deflections of the cylindrically shallow shell are less than that of the laminate.
2. From comparisons between present results for cylindrically shallow shell and finite-element results in Ref. [5] (see Fig. 4) it is found that when loads are lower both are coincident, and when loads are higher they are different to each other. And when load reaches $1.8(\text{psi})$ a phenomenon that the central deflection of the shell jumps to opposite direction will occur, which had not be reported in Ref. [5]. The shaps of crosssection at $x = a/2$ before and after the jump are shown in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) respectively.

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Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5